

**REDUCTIVE DEGRADATION OF 2,4-DICHLOROPHENOXYACETIC
ACID USING Pd/CARBON WITH ADSORPTION/CATALYSIS
BIFUNCTIONAL ROLES**

E. Castillejos^{1*}, A. Esteban-Arranz¹, B. Bachiller-Baeza^{2,3}, I. Rodríguez-Ramos^{2,3}, A. Guerrero-Ruiz^{1,3}

¹ *Dpto. Química Inorgánica y Técnica, Facultad de Ciencias, UNED, c/ Senda del Rey nº 9, 28040, Madrid, Spain*

² *Instituto de Catálisis y Petroleoquímica, CSIC, c/ Marie Curie Nº 2, Cantoblanco, 28049 Madrid, Spain.*

³ *Grupo de Diseño y Aplicación de Catalizadores Heterogéneos, Unidad Asociada UNED-CSIC (ICP), Spain.*

*Corresponding author: castillejoseva@ccia.uned.es

ABSTRACT

In this study, commercial carbon nanofibers with different graphitic structure and commercial multiwall carbon nanotubes (CNT) were used. Palladium catalysts were prepared using these supports. Subsequently, they were tested in the hydrodechlorination reaction of 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid under ambient-like conditions. Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and nitrogen adsorption at 77 K techniques were applied to characterize the different materials. We have demonstrated the efficiency of a bifunctional material in an integrated process that synergistically combines physical adsorption and catalytic degradation. During the process, the carbon surface provides active sites to get chlorophenoxyacetic adsorbed. After the saturation of the nanocarbon the compound was decomposed by the catalytic function of supported Palladium catalysts. We focus on testing the effects of the support surfaces and morphology of supported palladium nanoparticles on the catalytic performances. High selectivity to dechlorinated product was obtained with the catalysts prepared over more graphitic supports, whereas no-selectivity to dechlorinated took place over oxygen-containing support. The mechanistic aspects of this bifunctional process are postulated based on the characterisation of these catalytic materials.

Keywords: Nanocarbon; Adsorption; Catalysis, Hydrodechlorination; Palladium.

1. Introduction

Emerging pollutants (EPs) are synthetic chemicals that have the potential to enter into the environment. They can cause adverse ecological and/or human health effects, which are not commonly monitored and hardly removed from the aquatic media. Due to their low soil sorption and taking into account their high potential of leachability, these residues are often found on the surface and ground water. The consequent contamination caused by these EPs has attracted extensive attention due to their high toxicity and carcinogenicity effects. Chlorinated compounds are a group of these important chemical products, which are widely applied as end-products or intermediates in chemical and agrochemicals processes. Chlorophenoxy herbicides, like 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D), are also commonly used for the control of plant growth in many developing countries. They are applied through spraying onto open crop fields resulting in contaminated river and groundwater. During these years, many strategic techniques have been developed in order to remove these compounds, such as adsorption [1,2], oxidation [3], photocatalysis [4] and dechlorination methods [5,6].

Adsorption processes have been widely used as an alternative to other procedures due to its many advantageous characteristics such as: initial low cost, flexibility, simplicity of design and easiness of operation. However, the main disadvantage of these kinds of processes adsorption is the transference of the contaminants from water to another one, producing its disposal in the landfill. So a posterior treatment to fully eliminate them is required. Therefore, its experimental cost is still high due to the regeneration process of the spent adsorbents. Otherwise, the combination of an adsorption process with the posterior hydrodechlorination (HDC) reaction is defined as one of the most effective methods to separate and eliminate contaminants from the liquid phase. This hydrodechlorination pathway is characterized by the replacement of one or

more carbon bound halogen atoms with atomic hydrogen. Whereas adsorption and HDC reaction are well-established technologies, their combination for EPs abatement purposes has been employed in fewer cases.

Palladium (Pd) applications have emerged as a promising water strategic technology to eliminate a high number of priority contaminants in drinking water [7]. Also, it has been demonstrated that Pd provides higher specific HDC rates. Thus, we have implemented Pd as a catalytic model agent in this fundamental study, where it will be tested the role of different forms of carbon supports. Also, carbon nanomaterials were strategically chosen as supports due to their adsorption capacities and their indirect effects on activity and selectivity. Their different physicochemical characteristics influence the size, and morphology of the catalytic metal clusters on their surface, and consequently, the distribution of their reactive sites.

Therefore, the aim of this work is to combine a physical adsorption process and catalytic degradation reaction using Pd catalytic nanoparticles supported on carbon materials as an adsorbent/catalyst bifunctional material. During the adsorption from polluted water, the carbon surface provides adsorption sites to retain the chlorinated compound 2,4-D. Once the carbon is saturated, the 2,4-D molecules can be decomposed by the catalytic action of the Pd nanoparticles (NPs). Here, we demonstrate that the graphitic character and surface functionalization of model carbon supports alter their interactions with the palladium nanoparticles and consequently, the selectivity of the reaction. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) shows electronic modifications at the Pd–C interface, depending of the support, that are consistent with the observed changes in catalytic activity. The presented results demonstrate that the functionalities on carbon supports can alter both the surface chemistry and electronic properties of these bifunctional catalysts.

2. Experimental

2.1 Carbon supports

Different types of commercial carbon materials were used in this study, two Pyrograph III carbon nanofibers (CNFs): PR24-HHT and PR24-PS that were provided by Applied Sciences Inc. A commercial multiwall carbon nanotubes (3100 Series, 95% purity) obtained from Nanocyl™ was also used. The PR24-HHT CNFs (denoted as HHT) are originally treated at high temperature (~3300 K), possessing a stacked-cup morphology with a hollow core through the length of the fiber and also present a jagged outer surface with “round heads” or “loop” structures which connect several layers. The PR24-PS (denoted as PS) are pyrolytically stripped carbon fibers treated at 1373 K, and therefore, less graphitized than HHT. Finally, carbon nanotube sample (named as CNT) possesses multiple walls with a hollow inner core with both ends closed.

2.2 Preparation of supported palladium catalysts

Catalysts were prepared by wetness impregnation. The samples were immersed in an acetone solution of Pd(NO₃)₂, under alternative stirring and ultrasonic treatment. After 2 h, the solvent was removed under vacuum. The catalysts were prepared with a 1 wt % Pd loading. The exact metal content was determined by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) using a Perkin Elmer Optima 3300 DV equipment. The obtained results were similar to the nominal loading.

2.3 Supports and catalysts characterization

The Brunauer Emmet Teller (BET) surface area of the supports was measured from the nitrogen adsorption isotherms determined on a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 instrument. All the samples were also characterized by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and thermogravimetric analyses (TGA). XPS analysis was performed with an ESCA-PROBE P (Omicron) spectrometer by using non monochromatized Mg-K radiation (1253.6 eV). The spectral data for each sample were analysed using CASA XPS software. The relative concentrations and atomic ratios were determined from the integrated intensities of photoelectron lines corrected for the corresponding atomic sensitivity factor. TEM micrographs were performed on a JEOL JEM-2100F microscope at 200 kV. The samples were grounded and ultrasonically suspended in ethanol before the acquisition of the TEM images. The mean diameter of the Pd NPs was calculated based on a minimum of 300 particles. Average particle size (d_{TEM}) was calculated as $d_{\text{TEM}} = n_i d_i / \sum n_i d_i$ or $D_{\text{TEM}} = n_i d_i^3 / \sum n_i d_i^2$ where n_i is the number of particles with d_i diameter. Thermogravimetric analyses were conducted under helium in a TA instruments, model SDT Q600 TA System. The sample (~ 5 mg) was placed in a platinum crucible and heated up with a 10 °C /min ramp from 30 to 100 °C. This latter temperature was maintained for 30 minutes. Gases released during the TGA experiments are CO₂ and CO. It was evidenced by Temperature Program Detector-Mass Spec (TPD-MS) technique. The range of temperatures at which the evolution takes place is different; the amount of carboxyl can be estimated by the weight loss up to 723 K, while phenol-carbonyl groups correspond to the mass loss from 723 K up to 1100 K.

2.4 Hydrodechlorination experiments

The catalytic reduction of the catalysts was carried out at room temperature in NaBH_4 for 2 h. Then, the solid catalyst was added to a 250 mL flask reactor. Typically, an amount of 40 mg of catalyst was added to 80 mL of $65 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ reactant solution. Firstly, the adsorption process of 2,4-D was carried out at atmospheric pressure with high stirring (1200 rpm) for 1 h in order to study the effect of adsorption in the absence of H_2 . The reaction temperature was maintained at 25°C with a thermostatic water bath. After the adsorption equilibrium was reached, a H_2 flow ($10 \text{ mL}/\text{min}$) was fed into the reactor and then 2,4-D and catalysts started to react. The process was stirred at 1200 rpm in order to minimize external H_2 transport limitations. The samples were taken periodically and then filtrated with $0.45 \mu\text{m}$ membrane filter. The concentrations of the reactant and products were quantified by HPLC with an Agilent system that is equipped with a ZORBAX-RP C18 column with a UV/Visible detector at 283 nm coupled with mass spectrometer. A mixture of water and acetonitrile (50:50, V:V) and 1% formic acid was selected as a mobile phase. To calculate the equilibrium adsorption capacity, the following equation was applied $q_e = (c_0 - c_e)V/m$ where q_e is referred to the adsorption capacity (mg of 2,4-D/mg of carbon materials), c_0 (mg/L) is the initial pollutant concentration, c_e (mg/L) is the equilibrium concentrations, V is the solution volume (L) and m is the mass of the adsorbent (mg).

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Support characterization

The carbon materials used in this work were strategically chosen as supports due to their reduced structural and chemical complexity. PS consisted of a defined tubular structure terminated with a layer of disordered graphenic carbon. However CNT and HHT, characterized

in previous works by us [8], present higher graphitization degree and lower defect density character.

Characterization of the carbon materials was performed using a battery of techniques that includes BET, TGA and XPS. These techniques will provide valuable information to correlate the adsorption and catalytic performance of the different materials in the 2,4-D hydrodechlorination reaction.

In table 1 all BET values from the different supports are summarized. They were calculated from the adsorption isotherms of N₂ at 77 K. The equation was applied in the same range of relative pressures ($0.1 < p/p_0 < 0.3$). It was observed that all the samples have nearly the same type of isotherm that is characteristic of mesoporous materials with cylindrical shaped porosities.

Figure 1 displays the profiles of the TGA performed under helium and in Table 1 shows the total weight losses for all the supports are shown. It is well known that during the thermal treatment the oxygen functional groups decompose, releasing CO₂ (from the decomposition of carboxyl, anhydride and lactonic groups) and CO (from carbonyl, phenolic, quinones, pyrone and anhydride groups). The CO₂ and CO amount (mol/g) can be gravimetrically determined, considering the weight losses in the temperature ranges of 100-450 °C and 450-850 °C, respectively [9]. Results are summarized in Table 1. PS, HHT and CNT materials present a low amount of surface oxygen functionalities.

Table 1. BET surface areas, total weight loss determined gravimetrically and surface amounts of CO₂ and CO (mmol/m²)

Sample	BET (m ² /g)	Total weight loss%	mmol/m ² CO ₂	mmol/m ² CO
PS	36	2.09	0.003	0.020

HHT	32	0.80	-	0.003
CNT	285	1.80	0.001	0.002

Figure 1. TGA Profiles of the supports performed under helium

In general, PS support has more surface defects than CNT and HHT samples (originally heated up at high temperatures). Structural defects in graphitic based materials are considered as anchoring points to disperse Pd NPs even though additional effects must be considered to synthesize catalysts with optimal performance. Interestingly, deviation from the graphitic state is consistent with a charge transfer from Pd nanoparticles to the carbon support, so the magnitude of charge transfer depends on the carbon surface [10].

3.2 Characterization of catalysts

TEM was used to determine the dispersion, particle size and spatial location of Pd NPs in the different catalysts after their reduction and reaction. The TEM micrographs with their corresponding histograms of particle size distribution are exposed in Figure 2. Also, the mean particle diameters of Pd (calculated from TEM measurements) of the different reduced catalysts are shown in Table 2 and Figure 2. A similar range of particle sizes was detected. However, a different spatial localization of the Pd NPs for the distinct catalysts is observed. In the case of PS or HHT, Pd NPs are located on the outer surface and inside the 30 nm mesopore that extends along their main axis. Otherwise, in CNT, the PdNPs are located on their external surface due to the small inner diameter of CNT. In general, hemisphere Pd NPs are uniformly distributed on the carbon materials. So the fact that a similar Pd particle was found, indicate that it will not be a major responsible factor of the possible differences found in HDC activities with these catalysts.

Table 2. Average Pd diameter (nm) calculated from TEM

Sample	$d (\Sigma nd / \Sigma n)$ dr	$d (\Sigma nd^3 / \Sigma nd^2)$
Pd-HHT-dr	3.2	3.7
Pd-PS-dr	3.6	5.2
Pd-CNT-dr	3.1	5.7

Figure 2. The micrographs acquired for the spent catalysts: a) PdPs, b) PdHHT and c) PdCNT. The inserts show the particle size distribution.

The electron micrographs of reduced PdHHT or PdCNT (Fig. 2) revealed the presence of distortion or intimate interactions of the metal lattice at the Pd–C interface. The TEM images of PdHHT (Figure 2.b) show hemisphere Pd nanoclusters (293 atom of Pd) at the interface. They follow the curvature of the “round heads” or “loop” structures, suggesting that they bind to topological defects and to heteroatoms that decorate the amorphous sp^3 carbon and/or vacancies. In PdCNT micrographs, hemisphere Pd nanoclusters are also detected. In the case of PS supports (Fig. 2.a), the lack of contrast from nanoparticles with the support is probably caused by the thickness and/or high-scattering, which prevent the detection of the distortion.

XPS analyses were also performed on spent catalysts. The ratios between the atomic concentrations of elements are summarized in Table 3. It is clearly evidenced the presence of oxygen groups, chlorine and nitrogen on the surface of the materials. These last are due to the 2,4-D adsorption or Pd precursor on the surface of materials.

The XPS spectra for the doublet Pd $3d_{5/2}$ and $3d_{3/2}$ from the spent catalysts are shown in Figure 3. The value of Binding Energies (BE) at 336.2 eV (Pd $3d_{5/2}$) and 341.0 eV (Pd $3d_{3/2}$) suggests the presence of zero oxidation state of Pd in the spent catalysts. These high binding energies obtained for all catalysts could be ascribed to highly dispersed Pd NPs likely arising from electron transfer from Pd to support carbon atoms. This electron transfer is in line with the distortion images obtained by TEM. It is well known that the support can have an impact on the electronic properties of the metallic phase via metal–support interactions, which are more pronounced for Pd NPs at the nanoscale [11]. Highly dispersed Pd/C catalysts showed that the core level BE of Pd, significantly depends on its particle size shifting of 1.0-1.3 eV. [12,13,14,15]. A positive displacement of 1 eV was even observed by Jiang and co-workers for Pd NPs supported on carbon in comparison with bulk Pd [16].

The positive shift of binding energies was attributed to the size effect and the metal-support interaction for the Pd-based catalysts.

The second peak at 338.3 eV ($\text{Pd}3d_{5/2}$) for all samples can be assigned to Pd^{2+} species due to residual precursor or re-oxidized species upon NaBH_4 reduction. Significant differences were observed in the different catalysts. In the case of PdPS catalyst, palladium seems to be more oxidized than in PdHHT or PdCNT catalysts. Its O/C atomic ratios (Table 3) shows more oxygen content from the functional groups on PdPS. So the possibility of strong interactions between Pd^{2+} with these oxygen groups of the PS surface is enhanced [17,18]. Also, the nitrogen groups from the precursor or chlorine traces (Table 3) from 2,4-D adsorption on PS surface could also stabilize the existence of Pd^{2+} . Figure 4 shows the binding energy of Cl $2p_{3/2}$ (198.6–198.8 eV) that is attributed to the Cl^- anion, indicating the presence of HCl on PdPS surface. Moreover, the BE values at 200.1–200.3 eV indicate the presence of covalent chlorocarbon (C–Cl bond) compounds from 2,4-D in the PS surface. Otherwise, in PdHHT and PdCNT catalysts lower Pd^{2+} contribution was detected, possibly due to reduction of some Pd^{2+} species to Pd^0 .

Analyzing palladium spectrum of PdPS catalyst, the presence of an additional prominent signal at 337.4 eV is found. It can be fitted with three individual components or states of Pd at 336.2, 337.4 and 338.3 eV for Pd $3d_{5/2}$, which are referred to the coexistence of metallic and oxidized Pd species, respectively. The peak at 337.4 eV (only present on PdPS) could be assigned to electron-depleted palladium atoms in consequence of the charge transfer between the metal and the carbon support. This effect causes the existence of electron-deficient species Pd^{n+} . This binding energy is inconsistent with the values reported in the literature [19,20,21]. The broad shape of the peak indicates that the binding energy of Pd^{n+} species falls in a wider range than Pd^0 . In this sense, XPS is a powerful tool to probe variations of electron density or metal-carbon interaction in carbon supported

metal catalysts. Even if 5 nm Pd NPs are expected to display bulk-like properties [22], the charge depletion is large enough to influence their performance. These species can be formed in the catalysts prepared from Pd(NO₃)₂, even after NaBH₄ reduction, due to the interaction between electron-donor Pd⁰ atoms with neighbouring electron-acceptor species that are present on the carbon surface. The Pdⁿ⁺ is stabilized by the Cl⁻ ions, NO_x and oxygen functionalities located in the PS support. Regarding NO_x entities, stems from nitrate counter ion remain adsorbed on the surface. Figure 5 show XPS spectrum of N1s signal at 401 eV, which is assigned to decomposition products of nitrate [17]. The different functionalities found on PS served to modify the electron density of Pd sites with the formation of supported Pdⁿ⁺. Thus, support surface species alter both properties, the surface chemistry and the electronic properties, where the charge depletion layer could be large enough to influence the Pd NPs. Ramos et al. [23] reported a shift to higher BE for Pd supported on carbon that was attributed to electronic transfer associated with residual surface Cl. Gómez-Sainero et al. [17] have also demonstrated the existence of electron deficient Pd associated to the presence of surface species (e.g. HCl and NO_x) generated during catalyst preparation/activation that modified the electron density of the Pd sites with the formation of supported Pdⁿ⁺.

Table 3. XPS data of the spent catalysts

Samples	XPS atomic ratios			
	Pd/C	O/C	N/C	Cl/C
PdPS	0.003	0.070	0.011	0.002
PdHHT	0.004	0.006	0.009	-
PdCNT	0.001	0.015	-	-

Figure 3. XPS profiles of Pd 3d core-level spectra of the spent catalysts

Figure 4. Cl 2p core-level spectra of the spent PdPS catalyst

Figure 5. N 1s core-level spectra of the spent PdPS catalyst

3.3. Catalytic results

Liquid phase catalytic degradation of 65 mg/L of 2,4-D versus time in the presence of the previously reduced catalysts is shown in Figure 6. The first part of the figure corresponds to the adsorption phase in hydrogen absence. After the adsorption equilibrium was reached (60 min), a H₂ flow was fed into the reactor. Then, the second part of the figure displays the catalytic degradation of the 2,4-D. The figure shows almost zero 2,4-D concentration in the solution after 80 min in the case of PdCNT and PdHHT catalysts. Their rate constants were calculated applying a first order equation. The PdCNT has a rate constant of 1.16 min⁻¹, which is more than 60-times in comparison with PdPS and nearly 11 times better than the PdHHT catalyst.

PdCNT exhibited a high BET surface area (285 m²/g, recorded in Table 2), while the surface area of PdHHT or PdPS were only about 30 m²/g. PdCNT shows greater adsorption capacity than PdHHT and PdPS due to its higher BET surface area. However, PdHHT displays a greater adsorption capacity than PdPS even though their BET areas values are similar (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Liquid phase catalytic HDC over PdPS, PdHHT and PdCNT.

As far as the HDC reactions (taking place after 60 min when hydrogen gas is introduced in the reactor) are concerned, the PdHHT and PdCNT catalysts showed excellent activity to convert 2,4-D into phenoxyacetic acid (PA), which is the ultimate dechlorinated product, being 75% and 65% at 70 min, respectively. Interestingly, the observed trend diverges for PdPS. This catalyst only showed the partial dechlorinated product 2-chlorophenoxy acetic

acid (2-CIPA), which is 50% at 70 min. Phenoxy acetic acid was not detected. At the end, the concentration of 2-CPA was much higher than that 4-phenoxy acetic acid (4-CPA), being this only detected a maximum of 4 % with PdPS. These results have been verified by XPS where only chlorocarbon (C–Cl bond) compounds were detected on PdPS surface. The 2-CPA and 4-CPA are the partially dechlorinated products and PA is the ultimate dechlorinated product (Scheme 1) of the dehydrodechlorination of 2,4-D. The substituted Cl of 2,4-D can be eliminated by two stepwise routes with 2-CPA or 4-CPA as reaction intermediates or by the simultaneous removal of both substituted Cl obtaining PA [24]. This is a suitable model system to assess selectivity to ortho-Cl versus para-Cl. In this study the hydrogen solved gas was activated by Pd and then reacted with adsorbed 2,4-D on the support. Consequently 2-CPA, 4-CPA and PA were formed due to the break of the C-Cl bond. The concentration of 2-CPA was much higher than the 4-CPA, indicating a higher susceptibility for the para-Cl position to get eliminated in comparison with the ortho-Cl position . So chlorine atom located at the ortho position was much less reactive than that at para position as a result of steric hindrance [25]. The chlorine located at the para position was much more easily replaced by adsorbed reactive hydrogen because is surrounded by a much larger space than was the chlorine located at the ortho position. Subsequently the produced 2-CPA could react with active H to obtain PA.

Scheme 1. Dechlorination pathways of the catalytic HDC

Considering the reasons causing the differences found in the catalytic activities and selectivities for these catalysts, we should be aware that the Pd properties, such as particle size, particles shaped or Pd species are relevant to justify observed catalytic behaviour. Moreover, the carbon functionalities seem to determine the different metal-support interactions. TEM results indicated that very similar Pd shapes and particle sizes were detected in the catalysts. So this is considered as a minor factor for the differences found in HDC reactivities among these catalysts. Also, a similar loading does not respond to differences in activity or selectivity. Thus, the key factors that control the catalytic results seem to be: support polarity, support functionalities, metal nanoparticle species or adsorption of the 2,4-D.

3.3.1 Effect of 2,4-D adsorption on the support

The adsorption process has been considered as a critical step on HDC for many chlorinated organic compounds. The normalized adsorption capacity (q_e/S_{BET}) follows the order CNT (0.0025) \gg HHT (0.00029) $>$ PS (0.00014). The highest adsorption capacity of CNT or PS may be due to its higher hydrophobicity or mesoporous volume in the case of CNT. Besides, the oxygen groups of PS support (in comparison with HHT) may form hydrogen bondings with the water molecules, making it less available to adsorb 2,4-D onto this catalyst. This phenomenon is an accepted mechanism which reduces PS adsorption capacity due to the formation of water clusters through H-bonding with acidic surface groups [26]. The observed increase/decrease in the adsorption capacity may be consistent with the interactions between 2,4-D and the delocalized pi system of the HHT and CNT supports, or the hydrogen bondings with the water on PdPS catalyst.

3.3.1 Effect of the Palladium

The results showed that the catalysts with two phase of Pd, Pd⁰ and Pd²⁺ (mostly Pd⁰), are actives for the HDC reactions, whereas the catalyst that presents three species (Pd⁰, Pd²⁺ and Pdⁿ⁺) is less active. So it seems that the catalytic activity changes with the Pd electronic structure. Our findings indicate that its electronic effects is the most important factor to control the reactivity during the process. Moreover, similar NPs size does not have much importance. The effect of similar loading, particle sizes and particle shapes obtained from all PdPS, PdHHT or PdCNT indicate with the trends found in the catalytic performance that do not have a big impact. In general, HDC seems to be structure sensitive where the increase in NPs dispersion leads to a decrease in TOF. Diaz et al. [27] studied the HDC of the trichloroethylene where they found that largest Pd NPs were the most actives due to the

formation of palladium hydrides in the catalyst. However, other authors [28] reported that the hydrodechlorination reaction is not sensitive to the catalysts structure.

The coexistence of Pd²⁺/Pd⁰ in the catalysts could be essential for the effectiveness of the 2,4-D HDC, in which Pd⁰ is the active site for H₂ activation and Pd²⁺ is the active site for the activation of C-Cl bond. These results were consistent with previous studies [17]. The marked decreased in activity of the PdPS catalysts responds to the existence of Pdⁿ⁺ and the reduced adsorption of the 2,4-D. In this case, the lewis acid character of Pdⁿ⁺ served as the active site for the activation of C-Cl through a donor-acceptor bond with the Cl⁻ anion of the 2,4-D. The high density of unoccupied states of Pdⁿ⁺ enables it to accommodate one electron. Similar mechanisms were proposed by several authors in order to explain similar reactions [29,30,31]. We cannot discard the possibility that such values can be influenced by the poisoning effect of chlorine deposition.

3.3.1 Effect of the carbon structure

The evaluation from the influence of the support in the catalytic results is a difficult task. On the whole, the catalytic behavior can depend on the structure and nature of the nanocarbons used as support [32]. To study the effect of our supports on the catalytic activity, we chose catalysts with similar metal dispersion in order to minimize the effect of particle size. So the differences found in the conversion or selectivity for the HDC of 2,4-D are not correlated with the particle size. The role of the support during the HDC of 2,4-D must be analysed from different points of view. Stacked cup carbon nanotubes were strategically chosen as supports due to their reduced chemical or structural complexity. The catalytic results are not the consequence of differences found in mass

transport, size, surface area or porosity of the supports. However, significant differences in activity and selectivity were observed for the PS sample. Its selectivity to CPA is consistent with previous studies that suggested a correlation with the surface polarity [33]. Polar surfaces were proposed to favor adsorption through the terminal carbonyl functionality. The PS surface could respond to this behavior due to the induced polarity by the surface groups. Besides, the PS surface could favor the adsorption through the para-Cl terminal of the 2,4-D and the Lewis acid centres of this carbon surface by slightly electrostatic attraction. So, this adsorption-controlled mechanism could notably disfavor the ultimate dechlorinated product. Otherwise, planar adsorption mode is favored by non-polar surfaces such as CNT or HHT. The benzene ring of the 2,4-D and the delocalized pi system of the carbon support can enhance PA production. These results are consistent with the adsorption capacity of the different nanocarbons. A favorable effect on HDC has been found with hydrophobic supports such as nanocarbons, which is explained by facilitating the adsorption of the hydrophobic organic halide [34]. It's very unlikely that the initial catalyst activity could be related with the adsorption capacity of the support materials, because the HDC reaction needs Pd active centers, which are placed at long distances of the adsorption sites.

Under these circumstances the effect of the support has to be rationalized in terms of the metal-support interface. In this respect, PS supports can capture chloride species from 2,4-D adsorption that can poison the Pd clusters lead to the passivation of the catalyst. Graphitic surface of the HHT or CNT supports did not form halogenated species avoiding the gradual passivation of the catalyst. The results showed that the adsorbed species depends on the nanocarbon structure, suggesting the crucial indirect role of these structures.

4. Conclusions

In the present work, the differences found in the activity and selectivity with the different catalysts suggest a decisive role of the carbon surface. Three nanocarbon materials were compared both as adsorbents of 2,4-D and catalyst supports of Pd nanoparticles used in the HDC. Results indicate that the catalytic activity of the catalysts can be optimized by choice of the support. Notably, it can be correlated with the Pd metal phase and the support characteristics. The adsorption capacity of the support plays a decisive role, being very relevant for the catalytical process given that more points of reaction are revealed. Controlling the support surface characteristics such as functionalization or the graphitic character represents a strategy for turning the activity or selectivity of the catalysts. As significant results, PdPS showed incomplete HDC reaction even with similar particle sizes of Pd that PdHHT or PdCNT. Besides, this catalyst exhibited different HDC products. As a matter of fact the nanocarbon PS surface and the adsorbed water (in interaction with oxygen surface groups) synergistically leads to the incomplete catalytic decomposition of 2,4-D. Therefore, the support must be carefully selected, given that supports presenting strong interactions with the water molecules hinder the hydrodechlorination of the 2,4-D. On the other hand, the more graphitic catalysts showed a high resistance to poisoning by the chloride released upon the HDC reaction. Moreover our works expose trends between the charge distribution at the Pd NPs and the selectivity. In general our investigation also reveals how high graphitic surfaces combined with Pd nanoclusters synergistically joining physical adsorption and catalytic degradation, under very mild conditions (room temperature and atmospheric pressure hydrogen flow) of 2,4-D, so these materials can be considered as bifunctional catalysts. During the adsorption procedure, the carbon surface provides active sites to get chlorophenoxyacetic acid retained from the water phase. After

the nanocarbon is saturated with the reactant molecules, this last can be decomposed by the catalytic function of supported Pd catalysts. Undoubtedly, more research should be warranted in the future to determine the general rules that will enables the rational design of improved bifunctional catalysts.

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